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Essence of credit risk and assessment of customers' creditworthiness when paying off a car loan

KEYWORDS

car loans,
credit risk,
risk minimization,
secure lending model

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. The topic is relevant because, with the increasing demand for cars and the growth of car loans in recent years, banks and financial institutions need a more thorough assessment of customers' creditworthiness. In the highly competitive auto loan market, banks strive to improve their creditworthiness assessment methods to offer more favorable terms to customers. This creates the need for continuous improvement of approaches to credit risk assessment. Modern technologies such as big data, machine learning, and artificial intelligence are opening up new opportunities for more accurate assessment of customer creditworthiness.

The article aims to consider the essence of credit risk and develop proposals for minimizing it in car loans.

Materials and methods. The materials were researched in finance, banking, and credit risk and published in peer-reviewed scientific journals. The research methods were literature analysis and comparative analysis.

Results. Car loans are a common type of consumer credit and have fundamental distinguishing features of other kinds of loans. They are also an example of a complex interaction between a bank, a car dealership, a customer, and insurance companies. The statistics on the frequency of causes of non-repayment of consumer loans among individuals are analyzed. Measures to reduce the likelihood of non-repayment of car loans are proposed, and the possible positive and negative consequences of introducing these measures are considered.

Conclusion. With the development of technologies such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, and big data, new opportunities are opening up for more accurate and practical assessment of customer creditworthiness. This allows us to develop more complex models that can consider numerous factors and accurately predict the probability of default. Research related to assessing customers' creditworthiness when paying off car loans can help improve credit risk management methods, increase the financial stability of banks, and improve consumer protection.

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INTRODUCTION

Credit risks become more significant in economic instability, inflation, and changing market conditions. Assessing customers' creditworthiness and managing credit risk are becoming critically important to prevent losses and ensure banks' financial stability.

The topic is relevant because, with the increasing demand for cars and the growth of car loans in recent years, banks and financial institutions need a more thorough assessment of customers' creditworthiness. In the highly competitive auto loan market, banks strive to improve their creditworthiness assessment methods to offer more favorable terms to customers. This creates the need for continuous improvement of approaches to credit risk assessment. Modern technologies such as big data, machine learning, and artificial intelligence are opening up new opportunities for more accurate assessment of customer creditworthiness.

Currently, one of the most popular types of loans is car loans, that is, bank loans for purchasing motor vehicles, in most cases, while the car is secured.

Two types of car loans exist in banking practice: standard and commercial. A standard car loan is characterized by the maximum requirements for the borrower, the collateral, and the minimum cost of the loan. However, a standard car loan is not found in its pure form, as various car loan programs exist. A commercial car loan involves using the purchased car as a production tool.

Banks divide car loans into types based on the level and nature of the mortgagee's risk in debt repayment, so they set different loan terms.

Car loans, like other types of bank loans, are subject to risks. The specifics of this type of consumer loan primarily determine the dangers of car loans:

First, a car loan is always a loan to purchase a motor vehicle. This means that the probability of non-repayment of the loan is related to the client's creditworthiness and the car being pledged to the bank.

Second, the issuing a car loan is accompanied by the conclusion of a pledge agreement, according to which the pledgee accepts the pledge, and the pledgor transfers the vehicle which is the subject of the pledge under the agreement, as security for the fulfillment of obligations under the loan agreement. The collateral value of the car purchased by the customer must be specified in this agreement. The exception is the registration of an unsecured car loan. Importantly, the collateral remains the responsibility of the loan recipient. That is, the credit risk extends not only to the borrower but also to the vehicle.

Third, car loans often have several advantages over consumer loans, which include: a higher chance of borrower approval; a lower interest rate; a car loan is provided by wire

transfer of the loan amount to the checking account of the car seller, who is fully responsible for the transfer of ownership of the vehicle under the purchase agreement concluded with the buyer—sales; ease of registration.

Fourth, the car loan market assumes fierce competition, as car dealerships and banks choose car loans as a priority development area. The bank's share in the car loan sector is determined by several significant factors, including the bank's marketing, cost of additional services, work of managers, efficiency of the bank's mobile agents, and application processing time.

Fifth, car loans' distinctive features are a flexible schedule and increased customer orientation. This means the bank employee assigned to the remote service point is fully adjusted to the car dealership's work schedule. Therefore, loans can be issued outside the bank's and the employee's business hours.

In addition, a key feature of car loans is the interdependence of the bank providing the loan and the dealership selling the vehicle. The bank and salon employees closely interact with each other and are in an inevitable interdependence. This means that the client assesses the whole process without singling out the quality of service at the bank that issued the loan. Accordingly, the degree of customer loyalty to the bank directly depends on the salon's quality and speed of service. On the one hand, the interest in a common sale encourages cooperation and, to some extent, simplifies working with the client. However, cooperation has its drawbacks. There are often cases when a salon employee tries to win over a client to a partner bank by providing information about the terms of lending, the interest rate, and additional products of the bank. Due to the lack of awareness of car dealership managers, the information is often incomplete or unreliable, which leads to a decrease in customer loyalty.

The article aims to consider the essence of credit risk and develop proposals for minimizing it in car loans.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials were research in the fields of finance, banking, and credit risk, published in peer-reviewed scientific journals such as the Journal of Financial Stability, Economic Perspectives, Review of Economics and Finance, Transport Policy, Journal of Economics and Business, International Tax and Public Finance, Journal of Credit Risk, and Journal of Consumer Affairs.

Special publications devoted to credit risk and its assessment, as well as studies and reports from consulting companies on trends in car loans and credit risk, were also used.

Research methods: literature analysis, comparative analysis.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Deming Wu et al. developed an empirical model of car loan defaults using samples of car loans from two major credit bureaus. The authors found that loans aged five years or more carry a significantly higher probability of default. The researchers also found that the main problem of stress testing is the instability of the model. The results show that the coefficients of macroeconomic variables vary significantly in different sample periods and even have incorrect signs in specific periods. Consequently, banks and regulators often face the problem of model instability. For this reason, modelers need to perform a sensitivity analysis, create various benchmarks, and make conservative adjustments to minimize the risk of the model [1].

Agarwal et al. reported that approximately three-quarters of car purchases in the United States are financed by credit, and car loans are one of the most common forms of borrowing. Third party financing (direct loans) accounts for the most significant part of the automotive loan market, dealer financing (indirect loans) is in second place, and leasing is in third place. The authors identify the risks lenders often face in the automotive market. The first and most obvious risk is default, meaning a person who has taken out a loan to buy a car or truck cannot repay it. The second is the risk of early repayment, that is, the buyer of a car or truck repays the loan ahead of schedule, which reduces the flow of interest payments from the lender [2].

Y. Ghulam and S. Hill conclude that married and divorced borrowers, as well as borrowers living in regions with low unemployment and relatively prosperous areas such as the South-East and London, are less likely to default compared to unmarried people living in the north-west of the UK, who have a high probability of default. According to the authors, the characteristics that most affect the default status are the price and age of the car, the effective interest rate, the loan-to-collateral ratio, and the term of the loan agreement [3].

A. Walks examines the level of car-related debt among low-income households and the impact of living in areas with high levels of motorization, using the example of seven of Canada's largest metropolitan areas. The authors demonstrate the relationship between the level of motorization and a higher relative burden of household debt, especially on car loans [4].

Huiqiong Duan et al. believe that demographic characteristics and the level of corruption have predictive power in analyzing the risk of delay. For example, people from provinces with higher levels of bribery accumulate significantly more overdue payments. The authors also note that the borrower, having learned about the absence of punishment for late payment during the first 10 days, becomes more prone to delay [5].

A. Muthitacharoen et al. find that fiscal incentives cause financial difficulties and debt burdens. The authors use data on debts among creditors participating in the program to

purchase their first car in Thailand. According to the researchers, the development of incentive policies should focus more on productive business durable goods than on consumer goods [6].

Z. Guo et al. find that car loans with maturities of more than five years have higher delinquency rates than short-term loans during each year of their lives. The authors also find that interest rates on car loans for more than six years are getting lower over time compared to short-term car loans [7].

T. Salz et al. study the features of car loan intermediation through car dealers. The authors write that agreements between car dealers and lenders encourage dealers to raise loan prices [8].

N. E. Putri et al. identify customers' characteristics, behavior, and ways of retaining them in car loan companies. According to the authors, the car loan program respondents consider attractive is a special percentage and installment plan [9].

J. van Rijn et al. find that, on average, households that receive car loans from credit unions pay 0.70 percentage points less in interest rates for new cars and 1.40 percentage points less for used vehicles compared to similar households that receive car loans from banks [10].

A. R. Abu Talib Khan et al. study the effectiveness and competitiveness of Islamic car loans compared to traditional car loans, namely, installment purchases in Malaysia. According to the authors, Islamic car loans are becoming more competitive and are expected to surpass the volume of conventional loans starting in 2018 [11].

Thus, numerous approaches to determining credit risk exist, and its classification may vary depending on the context. Existing methods for assessing the creditworthiness of clients may be outdated or insufficiently accurate in a rapidly changing financial market. Therefore, developing and adapting new methods and models that consider modern realities, such as big data, machine learning, and other technologies, is necessary. With the development of technology and the emergence of new financial instruments (for example, P2P lending, FinTech solutions), studying their impact on credit risk and creditworthiness assessment is necessary.

Macroeconomic factors such as unemployment, inflation, changes in legislation, and economic stability can significantly affect customer creditworthiness and credit risk. Car loan clients also have various financial and social characteristics that can affect their creditworthiness.

RESULTS

The bank's credit risk can be defined as the maximum expected loss that can occur with a given probability over a specific period due to a decrease in the value of the loan portfolio due to partial or complete insolvency of borrowers by the time the loan is repaid.

Figure 1 shows the structure of credit risk.

Кредитный риск	Credit risk
Риск, связанный с заемщиком	Risk associated with the borrower
Риск, связанный с возвратом ссуды	Risk associated with repayment of the loan
Системный риск	Systemic risk
Форс-мажор	Force majeure
Риск гаранта	Risk of the guarantor
Риск страховщика	Risk of the insurer
Риск залога	Collateral risk
Объективный	Objective
Субъективный	Subjective
Юридический	Juridical
Ликвидность	Liquidity
Конъюнктуры	Conjunctures
Потери	Losses
Юридический	Juridical

Figure 1 Credit risk structure.

Source: compiled from the source [12]

According to Figure 1, collateral risk is a component of credit risk. This risk is significant in car loans; to reduce it, banks are developing various lending programs that allow them to divide vehicles into different categories.

Credit risks are classified into internal and external categories according to their source of manifestation [13].

External credit risks include the state and opportunities for economic development, credit, foreign and domestic policy of the country, and possible changes in government regulation. In turn, external financial risks are divided into country and force majeure.

Internal credit risks are related to the services provided themselves, that is, the product, its features, and the losses that are inevitable if the counterparty defaults.

A bank that provides car loans to customers can influence internal risks by analyzing and making necessary changes to products, parameters of additional products, and their costs. However, the bank cannot protect itself from external risks.

Depending on the creditworthiness of borrowers, there are several credit risk categories.

With minimal credit risk, the borrower has the highest chance of obtaining a loan at a low interest rate.

At the usual (average) level of credit risk, losses on loan operations are possible.

The maximum allowable level of credit risk assumes that the borrower pays the principal, but violates the payment deadlines.

Clients who cannot repay their debts promptly are assigned a high level of risk.

An unacceptable level of risk may mean that the client is either on the verge of bankruptcy or has repeatedly overdue a payment.

The risk management system is inextricably linked to establishing an acceptable risk level.

The modern concept of acceptable risk in strategic planning recognizes the risk of not implementing the plan, since it is impossible to eliminate the potential causes that may lead to undesirable developments.

Due to the need to determine the degree of credit risk, commercial banks are developing a system for monitoring lending-related activities.

According to Figure 2, the credit risk management process takes place in 5 stages.

Анализ уровня платежеспособности	Analysis of the level of solvency
Оценка возможного кредита	Assessment of a possible loan
Структурирование займа	Loan structuring
Оформление, выдача кредита	Registration and issuance of a loan
Контроль над заемщиком	Control over the borrower

Figure 2 Stages of credit risk management

Source: compiled from the source [14]

According to Figure 2, credit risk management has five stages. Essential measures are analyzing the borrower's creditworthiness, assessing a possible loan, and following up after the loan is issued.

Risk assessment, forecasting, and leveling are essential in implementing financial policy and affect all bank processes, from raising funds to repaying loans [15].

The risk management system in a car loan bank should be based on an integrated structure consisting of functions that descend from the Board level down to the operational levels, while including all aspects of risk, namely market, credit and liquidity risk, operational, legal risks, risks related to the bank's reputation and by the staff. This structure includes the management board as the ultimate responsible body, committees, a risk management department, and various support and control departments. All listed elements of the structure have clearly defined responsibilities and reporting procedures.

A modern commercial bank applies an individual system for assessing credit risks and ways to regulate them, based on the specific terms of the transaction, the bank's priority areas of activity, its competitiveness, relationships with the customer base, the level of economic and political stability in the country, and other factors [16].

Due to the specifics of car loans, credit risk assessment is carried out concerning the borrower and the vehicle, which is subject to mandatory verification.

One way to reduce financial risks when applying for a car loan is to conclude an insurance contract. Insurance is an integral component of the economic and social sphere, an essential element of the market infrastructure. It directly affects the interests of society and business entities, ensuring their protection.

Motor vehicle insurance as property – provides insurance coverage for a motor vehicle and additional equipment in case of their complete actual death, i.e. complete loss of the primary function of the product, or damage, i.e. partial loss of the primary function and (or) the main, secondary and side functions of the product [17]. The economic basis of insurance is the process of formation and expenditure of the insurance fund [18]. Insurance can be used to reduce credit risk in car loans.

Figure 3 Frequency of non-payment reasons

Source: compiled from the source [19]

There are many variations in the causes of overdue debt and absolute non-payment of debt under a consumer loan agreement under a car loan program by individuals.

Figure 3 shows the most common reasons for non-payment of debt under a consumer loan agreement.

According to Figure 3, the most common reasons for non-payment are contesting the debt amount and the client's financial condition.

Internal contradictions in the consumer lending market are the clash of interests of opposing parties, since the lender and the borrower see credit relations from their positions [20; 21].

Suggestions for minimizing risk in car loans

A car loan bank may resort to specific measures to reduce the likelihood of loan non-repayment.

Firstly, the risk may arise at the application stage due to the client providing false information to a bank employee. The situation is complicated because a certificate confirming the client's income or the accuracy of information about the place of work is not required when applying for a car loan.

One solution to this problem may be introducing mandatory telephone verification of all bank customers. However, this method will significantly increase the time for reviewing the client's application and reduce the bank's competitiveness. A requirement to provide a document confirming income or official employment may also serve as a solution.

Second, the credit risk of car loans is closely related to the vehicle pledged to the bank. The risk is most often caused by the discrepancy between the cost of the car and the parameters stated in the application. This discrepancy appears if the client does not have a down payment or chooses a car loan instead of a consumer loan for the sake of favorable terms to cash out the loan eventually.

If no down payment is required, the car dealership overestimates the cost of the car to avoid missing the sale and commission. That is, the dealership makes additional documentation, artificially increasing the price of the vehicle. The added value passes through the documentation as an initial payment. The repayment of the loan also takes place with the direct participation of the car dealership. In this case, the salon documents the customer's car purchase, but the car dealership owns the vehicle.

The only way to reduce credit risks in these situations is to strengthen control over dealers and analyze each application for overstatement by comparing it with the recommended market price for each make and model of car.

A common reason for subsequent non-repayment of the loan is the influence of the human factor during the transaction. In this case, the human factor refers to the employee's negligence, inattention, or deliberate violation of the rules for the sake of the transaction.

The following can reduce the influence of the human factor:

- strict regulation of working hours and the time of possible transactions;
- improved control over the activities of financial consultants;
- psychological consultations for bank employees.

Another way to reduce credit risk is to improve automated banking information processing programs which will avoid issuance errors and prevent erroneous approvals of applications.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

For one reason or another, a car loan bank is exposed to various risks on a daily basis. However, the main risk in car loans is credit risk.

Due to the specifics of car loans, credit risk assessment is carried out not only with respect to the borrower but also with respect to the vehicle, which is subject to mandatory verification.

Most measures aiming to reduce credit risk in car loans can decrease a bank's competitiveness and, as a result, lower profits.

Measures such as improving automated banking information processing programs and strengthening control over dealers do not carry additional risks associated with a market position; therefore, they are the best solutions for reducing risks.

With the development of technologies such as AI, machine learning, and big data, new opportunities are opening up for more accurate and practical assessment of customer creditworthiness [22]. This allows us to develop more complex models that can consider various factors and accurately predict the probability of default.

Thus, research on assessing customers' creditworthiness when paying off car loans can improve credit risk management methods, increase banks' financial stability, and improve consumer protection, making it relevant and vital in modern conditions.

REFERENCES

1. Deming Wu, Ming Fang, & Qing Wang. (2018). An empirical study of bank stress testing for auto loans. *Journal of Financial Stability*, 39, 79–89. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfs.2018.09.005>.
2. Agarwal, S., & Chomsisengphet, S. (2008). Determinants of automobile loan default and prepayment. *Economic Perspectives*, 32, 17–28.
3. Ghulam, Y., & Hill, S. (2017). Distinguishing between good and bad subprime auto

- loans borrowers: the role of demographic, region and loan characteristics. *Review of Economics and Finance*, 10(4), 49–62.
4. Walks, A. (2018). Driving the poor into debt? Automobile loans, transport disadvantage, and automobile dependence. *Transport Policy*, 65, 137–149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2017.01.001>
 5. Duan, H., Snyder, T., & Yuan, W. (2018). Corruption, economic development, and auto loan delinquency: Evidence from China. *Journal of Economics and Business*, 99, 28–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeconbus.2018.08.001>.
 6. Muthitacharoen, A., Samphantharak, K., & Chantararat, S. (2019). Fiscal stimulus and debt burden: evidence from Thailand's first-car-buyer tax rebate program. *International Tax and Public Finance*, 26, 1383–1415. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10797-019-09549-6>
 7. Guo, Z., Zhang, Y., & Zhao, X. (2018). Risks of Long-Term Auto Loans. *Journal of Credit Risk*. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3290841>. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3290841>
 8. Salz, T., Grunewald, A., Low, D., & Lanning, J. (2020). Auto Dealer Loan Intermediation: Consumer Behavior and Competitive Effects. NBER Working Paper, 28136. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3735703>
 9. Putri, N. E., Simanjuntak, M., & Yuliati, L. N. (2019). Car loan behavior and customer retention. *Russian Journal of Agricultural and Socio-Economic Sciences*, 90, 149–154. <https://doi.org/10.18551/rjoas.2019-06.20>
 10. van Rijn, J., Zeng, S., & Hellman, P. (2021). Financial Institution Objectives & Auto Loan Pricing: Evidence from the Survey of Consumer Finances. *Journal of Consumer Affairs*, 55. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joca.12392>
 11. Abu Talib Khan, A. R., Bidin, J., Abdul Jalil, M. A. N., & Ariffin, A. F. (2019). Constant Market Share Analysis of the Competitiveness of Islamic Car Financing and Conventional Car Loan in Malaysia. In: Mat Noor, A., Mohd Zakuan, Z., Muhamad Noor, S. (eds) Proceedings of the Second International Conference on the Future of ASEAN (ICoFA) 2017 – Volume 1. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-8730-1_33
 12. Klimchuk, S. V. (2020). Formation of a business model for effective credit risk management. *Vectors of regional development: successful practices of effective management. Collection of materials of the scientific and practical conference*. Sevastopol branch of the Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education "PRUE named after G.V. Plekhanov". Simferopol, 227–240.
 13. Latysheva, L. A. (2021). Financial risk management: textbook / edited by L. A. Latysheva; L. A. Latysheva, Yu. M. Sklyarova, Yu. I. Sklyarov. Stavropol, 12.
 14. Nikiforova, V. D. (2019). Theoretical and practical aspects of commercial banks' work with problem loans. *Scientific journal of NRU ITMO. Series: Economics and environmental management*, 3, 93–100.
 15. Dyakov, S. A. (2021). Credit Risk Management in a Commercial Bank. *Bulletin of the*

Academy of Knowledge, 43 (2), 379–384.

16. Tyumambayeva, A. G., & Abdeshova, A. Sh. (2021). Credit Business: A Textbook for Students of Economic Specialties. Uralsk, Zhangir Khan West Kazakhstan Agrarian and Technical University, 127.
17. Kozlova O. N. (2022). Insurance: A Textbook / compiled by O. N. Kozlova, E. A. Dolbnya. Kemerovo, Kemerovo State University, 40.
18. Dodorina, I. V., & Klimova, V. V. (2023). Transport Insurance St. Petersburg, Lan' Publ., 7.
19. Kovalenko S. B. (2019). Bank Loan Portfolio and Its Role in Preventing Credit Risk. *Bulletin of the Saratov State Socio-Economic University*, 1 (75), 101–104.
20. Avdeeva, V. I., & Kulakova, N. N. (2019). Consumer lending in Russia in modern economic conditions. *Bulletin of the Altai Academy of Economics and Law*, 9-2, 5–11.
21. Rao, C., Liu, Y., & Goh, M. (2023). Credit risk assessment mechanism of personal auto loan based on PSO-XGBoost Model. *Complex & Intelligent Systems*, 9, 1391–1414. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40747-022-00854-y>
22. Ratnadiwakara, D. (2021). Collateral Value and Strategic Default: Evidence from Auto Loans. *Journal of Financial Services Research*, 59, 209–240. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10693-021-00350-3>

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